

When the Front Door Moves: How AI Threatens Scholarly Communities and What Publishers Can Do

Today's guest post is by Ben Kaube and Steve Smith. Ben is the co-founder of Cassyni, a platform for helping publishers harness events, video, and AI to engage their journal communities. Steve is the founder of STEM Knowledge Partners and an independent consultant with over 25 years of experience in scholarly publishing, including leadership roles at Blackwell Publishers, John Wiley & Sons, Frontiers Media, and AIP Publishing.

Imagine a researcher typing a complex scientific query into one of today's AI-discovery and summarization tools. In seconds, they receive a concise, seemingly authoritative summary - no clicking through to journal websites, no navigating subscription paywalls, and no downloading branded PDFs.

To the researcher, this feels like pure convenience, perhaps even *magic*, but for publishers it looks like *disintermediation*. What does this mean for scholarly journals, the communities they nurture, and the integrity they safeguard?

This is no hypothetical scenario: it's already here. Tools such as [Google's AI Overviews](#), [Perplexity](#), and [ChatGPT](#) now deliver instant answers that bypass publisher websites entirely. What looks like a routine dip in referral traffic is in fact a rewiring of the very infrastructure that has sustained scholarly communities for decades.

A cautionary example can be found in the recent [collapse](#) of [Stack Overflow](#), the leading question-and-answer platform for software developers. Between early 2023 and late 2024, the site saw new user questions plummet from nearly 90,000 per month to under 30,000, ostensibly as a result of AI chatbots that provided users with direct answers from Stack Overflow without directing them to the site.

This decline wasn't just about a reduction in clicks for users or traffic to Stack Overflow – it also meant fewer human engagements, fewer new questions (the platform's equivalent to manuscript submissions), and ultimately fewer reasons for experienced curators to remain involved. Revenue soon followed suit, declining sharply as advertisers realized that bots don't buy products or get hired. The trajectory is clear: AI-driven convenience can rapidly disrupt community-driven platforms and long-standing commercial dynamics.

Could scholarly publishing face a similar trajectory? Early data suggest the answer is yes. Google's AI Overviews, rolled out globally in October 2024, are already having a similar impact on traffic to a variety of sites. One [usability study](#) found click-through rates dropped by as much as 66% when an AI-generated summary appeared above traditional search results.

For subscription-based publisher websites, this immediately translates into falling content usage and declining revenues. For open access publishers relying on APC income, there is a similar feedback loop – fewer readers mean fewer authors submitting manuscripts, which ultimately erodes future revenue and community growth. Even platforms primarily built around free, openly available content – such as [SSRN](#) and [ResearchGate](#) – are vulnerable. Their engagement and community vitality depend critically on consistent traffic from search discovery; a decline in visits threatens the influx of new content, discussions, and the active researchers who sustain these platforms' relevance.

Further warning signs are already apparent. Multiple publishers report privately that bot traffic (from [GPTBot](#), [OAI-SearchBot](#), [ClaudeBot](#)) is outpacing genuine researcher visits. [Surveys reveal that researchers increasingly rely on AI summaries](#) rather than journal abstracts for their initial literature reviews.

Editorial flags about integrity and peer review quality concerns are rising, highlighting the erosion of human oversight networks traditionally supported by journal communities.

Yet despite these challenges, researchers' fundamental needs haven't changed. They still seek trusted communities to stay informed, debate emerging findings, develop collaborations, gain community recognition, and build their careers. The journal community, anchored in authentic human interaction, remains a crucial ecosystem amidst the noise of AI-generated content.

So, what can publishers do to remain resilient?

First, they must clearly encode trust signals – metadata readable by both humans and AI – to safeguard quality and context. Initiatives like [eLife's "Reviewed Preprint"](#) model show that when peer-review information is embedded in a standards-compliant, machine-readable format, it becomes a powerful alerting mechanism -- flagging higher-confidence research for both people and the algorithms they increasingly rely upon.

Crossref's machine-readable metadata, which enables implementation of the [FAIR \(Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable\) principles](#), similarly demonstrates how embedding clear, machine-readable metadata can alert researchers and algorithms alike when accuracy is crucial. A [recent study](#) highlighting that ChatGPT cited retracted cancer-imaging articles in around 10% of its answers underscores the urgent need for high-quality, structured, machine-readable retraction metadata to preserve research integrity.

Publishers can further reinforce trust by introducing visual markers – such as [ORCID](#) trust markers or the [Signals](#) badge – to highlight credible content or surface potential issues. This added transparency, comparable to Taylor & Francis's "[currently under investigation](#)" banner, visibly reinforces trustworthiness and accountability.

Second, publishers should rethink how they approach engagement metrics. Rather than narrowly optimizing for traditional COUNTER metrics or basic "usage," the goal should be meaningful, differentiated user experiences that foster genuine engagement. Publishers can add substantial value through multi-format content, such as video abstracts, interactive seminars, infographics, comprehensive supplementary materials, datasets, and easily digestible summaries (similar to Mayo Clinic's well-known "[easy-to-understand](#)" information format). Curation also presents significant opportunities here; carefully crafted

virtual collections can bring together diverse content types – including articles, books, conference proceedings, podcasts, and videos – in a coherent manner that adds clear value, with opportunities for collection editors to add commentary, nuance, and contextual insight.

Finally, the value of real human engagement cannot be overstated. Publishers must actively nurture authentic community interactions, for example, by hosting webinars, hybrid conferences, Reddit AMAs, Slack Q&As, and mentor cafés – similar to the successful programs run by the [Royal Society Publishing](#) and [AIP Publishing](#). Societies, with their established memberships, conferences, and existing communities, are particularly well positioned to excel here. Providing authors with more prominent profiles and greater opportunities to directly promote and discuss their work – through seminar series, "[Behind the Paper](#)" posts (such as those pioneered by Springer Nature), and other interactive formats – can significantly enhance community vitality and author engagement, particularly critical in today's AI-saturated information landscape.

Publishers should embrace, rather than resist, the upsides of AI discovery tools. Intelligent summarization can uncover hidden gems, helping researchers discover niche or older content that might otherwise go unnoticed. Publishers who proactively leverage AI tools to extend their reach will find themselves better positioned in this rapidly evolving environment.

The collapse of Stack Overflow is not just an intriguing anecdote, but also an important lesson for scholarly publishing. Publishers who recognize the threat of AI-driven disintermediation and proactively build resilience through trusted metadata, differentiated content experiences, and vibrant, authentic community engagement will continue to thrive. Those who chase yesterday's metrics risk becoming invisible – cited by no one, read by no one, trusted by no one.

The future has already arrived. Publishers have a narrow window to respond thoughtfully and strategically. The choice is stark: adapt or risk becoming invisible.